

Results of Step 2/3 solutions for the 23 test sets

L. Lindegren
Lund Observatory

Introduction

In November 1987 I proposed to use simulated data for 23 particular RGC's in order to test the main reduction chain within NDAC. The RGC's and data intervals were chosen so that a small area around ($\alpha = 0.9927, \delta = 0.4206$), approximately coinciding with the Pleiades, would be included in all the data sets (assuming a nominal scanning law with $\bar{\nu}_0 = 221^\circ$, starting at J1989.5 and lasting for 2.5 years). Sets of raw data for these intervals were subsequently generated at RGO, using the provisional Input Catalogue IC1 as the *true* sky and a perturbed version of IC1 as the *a priori* catalogue. After processing at RGO, the catalogues and reduced data were transferred to CUO and, after great-circle reduction, to LO. Here we performed the last steps of the reductions, the sphere solution and determination of astrometric parameters (Step 2/3).

The tapes received in Lund were: LCUO9002 (end of August '89) and LCUO9003 (mid-december '89). Both tapes contain the results of reductions based on the same 23 sets of raw data, but with different conditions for the reductions. The first tape contains results from reductions using the 'true' catalogue and attitude (along with the true catalogue). For the reductions on the second tape, the 'perturbed' catalogue had been used both at RGO and CUO, resulting in a slightly erroneous attitude as well as a contribution to the abscissa errors due to the uncertainty in the ordinates. (The data on the second tape are thus representative of a 'first iteration' reduction, before the catalogue has been improved; the first tape may represent the situation in the 'final iteration'.)

Between the two tapes there was also a change of interface specifications: the first tape was written according to GCIS-4 and GCOS-2 (Sept-Dec '88), while the second tape follows GCID-5 (Nov '89).

Table 1 gives the start and end times of the 23 sets (in seconds from J1988.0), the number of stars observed in each set, and the equatorial coordinates of the RGC poles. Figures 1a-d show the distribution of stars on the sky according to the number of sets they were observed in (N_{obs}).

Reading and sorting the data

No difficulty was experienced in reading the data. The input routines are now written to be compatible with any interface version number from 4 and upward. (Thus the same routines were used for reading both tapes.)

Sorting the abscissae (using the program SORT23) went without problem. 53,905 observations of 32,727 stars were found (same on both tapes). The preparation program PREP23 was used to create a working catalogue (in the form of a direct access disc file) from the COOR-file also contained on the tape. For practical reasons, only the 'true' catalogue (from the first tape) was used for this purpose.

Two anomalies were found when inspecting the contents of the COOR-file. First, it appears that the B magnitude is consistently given instead of H_p in the coordinate records (item HIPMAG). Second, the reference epoch (item EPOCH) is given as 63158336 (seconds from J1988.0), which translates to 1990 Jan 01, 11^h58^m56^s TDT, or J1990.0 + 43136^s. I suppose the intended epoch is J1990.0 or $2 \times 365.25 \times 86400 = 63115200$ seconds from J1988.0. Fortunately these anomalies are of no consequence for the further reductions.

The main solution programs ACCU23 and SOLV23

The first attempt to run the main reduction programs failed completely. This led to the discovery of a serious bug. (In one of the subroutines, the great-circle reduction number IDGCR was confused with an internal numbering of the sets. This had had no effect on all previous simulation runs, where the IDGCR always coincided with the internal set number.)

After correcting this bug the reductions proceeded nominally. Of the 32,727 stars only 420 were accepted as primary reference stars and adjusted; the remaining 32,307 stars had too few observations. The normal equations matrix for the 23 zero points had an estimated condition number of about 10^5 , and the maximum number of bits lost in the Cholesky reduction was 22 (out of the 55-bit mantissa). This is much worse than expected for a 'full' solution (with at least some 500 sets covering the whole sky), but gave no apparent numerical problems.

Solutions based on the true catalogue and true attitude

The 420 adjusted stars were all observed in at least six sets ($N_{\text{obs}} \geq 6$). Results after preadjustment (i.e., before the zero points had been updated) are shown in Figure 2 and Table 2. The dispersion of the (calculated - true) parameters is large even after recursively removing obvious outliers (about 10% of the data). Restricting the analysis to 79 stars with $N_{\text{obs}} \geq 12$ gave the much better results shown in Figure 3 and Table 3. The corresponding solution for the set zero points is shown in Table 3a.

After application of the set zero points, a second (final or post-) adjustment of the astrometric parameters gave the results in Figure 4 and Table 4 (stars with $N_{\text{obs}} \geq 12$ only). The results are in some respects worse than after the preadjustment (Figure 3), showing that the zero point solution is not stable enough to produce sensible corrections. This is hardly surprising in view of the extremely unfavourable geometry of these sets. The updates to the set zero points after postadjustment of the astrometric parameters were extremely small (about 1 mas rms), indicating that the exact solution was indeed reached with the postadjustment.

Solutions based on the perturbed catalogue

Only the 79 stars with $N_{\text{obs}} \geq 12$ were analysed in detail. Figure 5 and Table 5 give the results of the preadjustment, Table 5a the zero point solution. The rms zero point correction is about 5.8 mas, which is consistent with an rms *a priori* positional error of about 0.25 arcsec.

However, the solution after application of the set zero points (Figure 6 and Table 6) is now much worse than before, especially for the parallax, where the distribution is strongly bimodal (this is vaguely suggested also in Figure 4). It turns out that the parallax errors are all positive in the Pleiades region (e.g., for INCA numbers below 50,000), and negative in the anti-Pleiades region of the sky (cf. Figure 6a). This is easily explained in terms of the geometry of these sets: if, in a given set, the parallax factor (projected on the RGC) is f in

the Pleiades region, then it is $-f$ in the anti-Pleiades region. Therefore, parallax biases by q and $-q$ arcsec in the two regions can both be ‘explained’ by the same abscissa shift of qf arcsec. In the normal (full-sky) geometry this bias effect is prevented by the occurrence of zero parallax factors at two points on every RGC, which effectively determine the abscissa zero points as far as the parallaxes are concerned.

Slit errors

The mesh algorithm correctly determines the slit errors for all stars with at least 12 observations. For stars with fewer observations there are numerous cases where an incorrect position is found, as shown in Figure 7.

Conclusion

The Step 2/3 part of the system test has verified the CUO/LO data interface and demonstrated that the ‘true’ astrometric parameters can be retrieved at the expected level of accuracy (i.e., a few milliarcsec). That the RGC zero point updating did not produce sensible results is only to be expected in view of the very limited sky coverage of the 23 sets.

Table 1. Characteristics of the 23 test sets (start and end times, number of stars, RGC pole coordinates).

IDGCR	Tbeg	Tend	N	R.A.	Dec.
20	48073548	48114923	1870	2.531212065995	-.079592067310
46	49060002	49103200	2591	2.926514970120	.650373173975
47	49103202	49146400	2578	2.923899904445	.687591197707
123	52018935	52056406	1971	2.332877746544	-.477766436983
208	55278028	55321227	2714	2.852780854538	.557889210479
209	55321228	55361067	2514	2.825779843320	.529117149643
210	55364428	55407627	2599	2.799084923007	.496377603018
215	55552236	55595435	2395	2.719110994154	.345351573856
216	55595436	55637803	2337	2.707144197869	.308945037395
217	55637804	55681003	2284	2.696886425123	.271842904431
509	66834935	66878134	2342	6.230178424673	-.844503181761
578	69490935	69534134	2243	5.548371756763	.348034116826
609	70681335	70724534	2522	5.981236221168	-.557344694784
610	70724535	70767734	2556	6.022111747052	-.574931673546
901	81894135	81937334	2086	2.347408078505	-.459729331791
963	115954935	115998134	2065	2.340167514881	-.439227709755
1008	84274935	84318134	2285	3.093188674698	.849398390191
1290	86002935	86046134	2180	2.435252979897	-.279735336866
1340	96831735	96873003	2571	6.130207492294	-.736546653075
1393	98751735	98794934	2216	5.466049761815	.480578078647
1681	100786935	100830134	2473	6.169318487490	-.804022435365
1723	111846135	111889334	2089	2.425961313032	-.296164288265
1788	113458935	113502134	2424	3.049171097096	.796114865618

Table 2. Average errors (computed minus true) and sample standard deviations after pre-adjustment (tape LCUO9002). Units are mas and mas/yr. The last row gives the number of rejected/retained data points out of 420 stars with $N_{obs} \geq 6$. (See also Figure 2.)

Parameter:	α	δ	Π	μ_α	μ_δ
$\langle C-T \rangle$	+1.12	-0.34	+0.05	-2.07	-3.69
s.d.	13.36	11.01	2.57	18.56	18.18
rej/ret	41/379	57/363	57/363	44/376	46/374

Table 3. Same as Table 2 but for 79 stars with $N_{obs} \geq 12$. (See also Figure 3.)

Parameter:	α	δ	Π	μ_α	μ_δ
$\langle C-T \rangle$	+0.87	-0.10	-0.30	+0.46	+0.17
s.d.	1.18	0.68	1.25	1.44	1.15
rej/ret	7/72	10/69	2/77	10/69	8/71

Table 4. Same as Table 3 but after adjustment of the RGC zero points. (See also Figure 4.)

Parameter:	α	δ	Π	μ_α	μ_δ
$\langle C-T \rangle$	+1.02	+0.01	-0.54	+0.23	+0.17
s.d.	1.13	0.90	1.96	1.54	1.04
rej/ret	7/72	7/72	0/79	9/70	9/70

Table 5. Results of the preadjustment of data from tape LCUO9003 (79 stars with $N_{obs} \geq 12$). See also Figure 5.

Parameter:	α	δ	Π	μ_α	μ_δ
$\langle C-T \rangle$	+5.15	-0.09	+0.09	+6.98	-0.78
s.d.	1.57	2.23	2.17	3.07	2.30
rej/ret	8/71	7/72	2/77	10/69	9/70

Table 6. Same as Table 5 but after adjustment of the RGC zero points. See also Figure 6.

Parameter:	α	δ	Π	μ_α	μ_δ
$\langle C-T \rangle$	+3.90	-0.10	+0.85	+7.71	-0.43
s.d.	0.99	0.86	8.33	3.11	2.05
rej/ret	11/68	13/76	1/78	7/72	10/69

Stars with $N_{\text{Obs}} \geq 1$

Stars with $N_{\text{Obs}} \geq 3$

Figure 1a-b. Distribution of stars with at least 1 and 3 observations.

Stars with $N_{\text{Obs}} \geq 6$

Stars with $N_{\text{Obs}} \geq 12$

Figure 1c-d. Distribution of stars with at least 6 and 12 observations.

Figure 2. Calculated minus true parameters for stars with at least 6 observations.

Figure 3. Calculated minus true parameters for stars with at least 12 observations (preadjustment of 9002)

Table 3a. Results of the RGC zero point solution for test tape LCU09002

ZERO POINT SOLUTION, run# 701 :

rms zero point update = .796015 mas (set# 11)

absolutely largest update = -2.053616 mas (set# 11)

rms zero point corr. = .796015 mas (set# 11)

absolutely largest corr. = -2.053616 mas (set# 11)

DETAILED ZERO POINT RESULTS:

set#	IDGCR	value	update	m.e. [mas]
1	20	-.707046	-.707046	.21811
2	46	-.343935	-.343935	1.020135
3	47	-.554022	-.554022	.298730
4	123	1.046744	1.046744	.977721
5	208	-.273903	-.273903	.488796
6	209	-.322884	-.322884	.308608
7	210	-.085353	-.085353	.186684
8	215	.767962	.767962	.216026
9	216	.510805	.510805	.252564
10	217	-.740678	-.740678	.286721
11	509	-2.053616	-2.053616	1.952670
12	578	1.160793	1.160793	1.718166
13	609	-.121325	-.121325	.685462
14	610	-.888774	-.888774	.970661
15	901	.904963	.904963	1.273365
16	963	-1.742880	-1.742880	1.639056
17	1008	-.129788	-.129788	.759548
18	1290	.020648	.020648	1.307415
19	1340	.249022	.249022	2.159345
20	1393	-.656201	-.656201	.348069
21	1681	.191596	.191596	.585809
22	1723	-.398843	-.398843	1.444223
23	1788	-.188070	-.188070	.383097

Stars with: $N_{obs} \geq 12$

Figure 4. Same as Figure 3 but after adjustment of abscissa zero points according to Table 3a.

Table 5a. Results of the RGC zero point solution for test tape LCU09000

ZERO POINT SOLUTION, run# 801 :

rms zero point update = 5.801589 mas (set# 20)
 absolutely largest update = -12.261428 mas (set# 20)

rms zero point corr. = 5.801589 mas (set# 20)
 absolutely largest corr. = -12.261428 mas (set# 20)

DETAILED ZERO POINT RESULTS:

set#	IDGCR	value	update	m.e. [mas]
1	20	-11.098166	-11.098166	.214917
2	46	3.032041	3.032041	1.006414
3	47	-8.290430	-8.290430	.293869
4	123	5.816821	5.816821	.964188
5	208	5.291548	5.291548	.481774
6	209	7.100986	7.100986	.304259
7	210	3.519569	3.519569	.184499
8	215	-1.537165	-1.537165	.214876
9	216	-1.368884	-1.368884	.251993
10	217	-4.968826	-4.968826	.284755
11	509	1.609034	1.609034	1.926467
12	578	-2.686840	-2.686840	1.694969
13	609	-4.594809	-4.594809	.676305
14	610	2.605710	2.605710	.958008
15	901	-.728686	-.728686	1.256137
16	963	-6.211225	-6.211225	.377892
17	1008	10.214605	10.214605	1.617022
18	1290	-1.021141	-1.021141	.749610
19	1340	8.394400	8.394400	1.289997
20	1393	-12.261428	-12.261428	2.130298
21	1681	1.853658	1.853658	.343292
22	1723	-3.063873	-3.063873	.578253
23	1788	1.908943	1.908943	1.424956

Stars with N_obs >= 12

Figure 5. Calculated minus true parameters for the sets on tape LCU09000 (preadjustment only)

Stars with $N_{\text{obs}} \geq 12$

Stars with $N_{\text{obs}} \geq 12$
and $ID \leq 50,000$

Figure 6. Same as Figure 5 but after adjustment of the abscissa zero points according to Table 5a.

Figure 6a. Same as Figure 6 but only for stars in the Pluicides region.

Calc-true positions for $N_{\text{obs}} < 6$

Calc-true positions for $N_{\text{obs}} \geq 6$

Figure 7. Plots of the positional errors for stars with too few observations for successful elimination of slit errors.